

Exploring Areas of the Brain Related to Dysmusia

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Introduction

There have been many recorded cases of proficient musicians losing their ability to read sheet music while retaining their ability to read English or vice versa. Researcher and amateur pianist Ian McDonald documented the aftermath of his stroke, noting his spared reading abilities despite his impaired ability in reading musical syntax and arithmetic (McDonald, 2006). Another professional musician lost her ability to read sheet music after suffering from a case of acute encephalitis (an inflammation in the brain) yet retained her mathematical and linguistic abilities (Cappelletti et al., 2000). Yet another instance had a piano teacher losing her ability to read sheet music while her reading ability remained mostly intact (Polk & Kertesz, 1993). These cases suggested a separate neural network needed for reading musical syntax, unique from both the neural networks used to read letters and the neural network used to read mathematical symbols. This was proved by researchers Wong and Gauthier, who found that reading musical syntax activated a vast neural network. Some areas of the brain activated while processing musical syntax were distinct from areas of the brain activated by reading English letters or Roman numerals (Wong & Gauthier, 2010). The deficiency in this network has been coined as “dysmusia”, which is defined as the “difficulty with learning to read music despite normal intelligence and opportunities” (Cuddy & Hébert, 2006).

Dysmusia is a widely observed phenomenon. Doctor Elizabeth Morrow informally surveyed 84 music instructors and string directors and found that 96.5% of them had had students who struggled with sheet music far more than their peers despite receiving the same instruction (Morrow, 2017). These findings all suggest strong anecdotal evidence for the existence of dysmusia; however, there has been very little research done on the subject. As a result, there are no conclusive pieces of evidence that prove its existence, no diagnostic criterion,

and no guidelines to assist kids who disproportionately struggle with reading musical syntax. In Morrow's study, 50% of the kids who struggled eventually dropped out of their respective music programs (Morrow, 2017). This study aims to take the first steps to understanding this issue by consolidating the scattered studies to form a more cohesive picture of what dysmusia might look like to look for trends in brain areas that are affected in order to gain more insight into potential causes and potential comorbidities. Thus the question: What are the potential brain areas that, if impaired, can cause dysmusia?

The literature around reading itself has been evolving throughout the past decades, and the functions that many areas of the brain perform in humankind's ability to decode syntax are still up for speculation. The region of our body that processes language is the brain, and it is split into four major lobes — the parietal lobe, the occipital lobe, the temporal lobe, and the frontal lobe (Jawabri & Sharma, 2023). Each of these four lobes has several subregions that perform their respective individual functions. The lobes are generally divided into “left” and “right” hemispheres. The corpus callosum sits in the center of the brain, acting as a bridge between its left and right hemispheres (Blaauw & Meiners, 2020). All four lobes are activated upon reading musical syntax (Wong and Gauthier, 2010). Particular areas that were identified include Broca's area, which is associated with language production, the dorsal visual stream, which communicates spatial processing and is located in the parietal and occipital lobes, and various parts of the temporal lobe, which process sensory information (Sergent et al., 1992; Maess et al., 2001; Calma-Roddin & Dury, 2020). Music is speculated to require different processing because it requires both spatial and rhythmic awareness, something language lacks (Benggsston & Ullén, 2006). This is further supported by the activation of the superior parietal lobe, which deals with spatial awareness and remains inactive when reading the written language (Sergent et al., 1992).

Musical syntax is unique in that it theoretically requires the understanding of musical sounds to understand the musical syntax (Maess et al., 2001). Musical abilities are theorized to be processed on the right side of the brain (Basso & Capitani, 1985 and Maess et al., 2001) The specific localisation of those musical abilities seem to be affected by other factors such as innate music aptitude, age, and assigned gender at birth (Brust, 2006 and Peretz, 2006); however, how those factors specifically influence people's musical abilities is currently unknown. Nonvisual areas of the brain also aid in music processing (Wong & Gauthier, 2010). The link between the written notes and the sounds that are played is speculated to be from the right supramarginal gyrus, which is located in the parietal lobe and is used to store and manipulate sounds (Maess et al., 2001 and Vachha & Middlebrooks, 2022). It is only activated when simultaneously reading and listening to music (Maess et al., 2001). This is anecdotally supported by an individual describing their difficulty understanding syntax as an inability to connect the notes with the sounds they represented. These challenges arose following a stroke that impaired their right angular and supramarginal gyri (McDonald, 2006). The idea of a multifaceted network is further supported by Judd et al., who report that there are no convincing cases of isolated dysmusia, where the ability to read sheet music is affected with no other issues arising (Judd et al., 1983). With an expansive and diverse neural network in play, impairment of any (or multiple) of those areas would lead to impairments in other functions.

Current data around this topic is very scant and very scattered. Many studies conducted around this topic are isolated case studies, which makes it difficult to determine overall trends from individual examples. Other studies only reference a few key studies like Sergent et al., excluding a large portion of the studies that have been conducted in the past. This leads to the same few studies being regurgitated ad nauseam, with many studies and their information left by

the wayside, which also makes it harder to access them. The regurgitation of the same few studies also leads to stagnant and possibly fallacious information, as it comes from only a few sources. The studies that do exist are disconnected from each other. A key example of that is the terminology being used being inconsistent. Many studies use the term “amusia” to describe both the inability to read musical syntax and discern the difference between pitches, but these are two distinct abilities, and people have displayed one ability while lacking the other (Midorikawa et al. 2003). Other researchers do make the distinction between amusia and dysmusia, but this further muddies the waters when researchers reference “amusia” because it often makes it hard to tell what precisely they are referencing. Some researchers have coined “amusia” to mean deficiency in any type of music ability whatsoever. While there have been a few attempts to compile studies centered on dysmusia as it is defined in this study, most of these systematic reviews were done over a decade ago, with the largest one done in 1983, and our understanding of syntax comprehension has greatly evolved since then. A few researchers conducted meta analyses on dysmusia in tandem with dyslexia, but that made it harder to isolate what parts of the brain are specifically interfering with musical syntax. This study was conducted as a meta analysis to create a holistic compilation of all available case studies that have been conducted in the past to identify overall trends in those who have been afflicted, focusing on the potential causes, difficulties with letters and mathematical symbols, and recovery.

Methodology

Eighty-seven sources were compiled across a variety of different journals and databases, which include the American Psychological Association, Nature, PLOS One, the New York Academy of Sciences, and Brain. Because of the extremely limited amount of studies, the only

initial inclusion criteria were that the studies focused on people's comprehension of music in some form, whether auditory or written. As the subject was relatively unknown in the eyes of the general public, searches often bore little results. Instead, studies were primarily found by looking into relevant citations in research studies' references. These studies were then entered into a spreadsheet, where they were tagged based on the type of study they used (or if they were a secondary source) and what topics they mentioned. These included four potential topics: reading music, listening to music, how people comprehend music as its own language (shortened to "music as a language"), and any mentioned case studies. There were two additional tags for other miscellaneous topics mentioned and general irrelevance. All studies that did not have the "reading music" tag were then excluded, which left 45 studies. It was then further narrowed down to exclude all studies that did not reference any case studies and were not case studies themselves. Several of the systematic reviews referenced a large number of other case studies conducted in the past, which brought the final count to 57 case studies that studied a total of 82 trained individuals of varying degrees of music ability, ranging from professional composers to schoolchildren who were studying instruments. Those case studies were then entered into a spreadsheet (see appendix for full dataset), where they were sorted by age and gender, to determine potential demographics that were more at risk; whether or not they recovered, to determine the likelihood of recovering from the affliction; mathematical and linguistic ability, to determine if there was overlap with other syntactic processing functions; musical ability, to determine if musical listening and musical reading were connected; and what area of the brain they suffered an affliction to before losing their ability to read music. The areas of the brain were determined to cause the development of dysmusia by their subjects only developing the difficulty after suffering a specific affliction in a mentioned area of the brain. These areas were highlighted

in yellow. A few case studies developed dysmusia after suffering an unspecified stroke, and as that was another semi-common phenomenon, those studies were highlighted in green. Case studies with dyslexic subjects had the cause labeled as “Unknown”, as those subjects had always struggled with reading sheet music and thus had no definitive cause. However, as there were a high number of subjects who were dyslexic, case studies with dyslexia were highlighted in orange to identify a potential overarching trend. Subjects who had other forms of neurodivergence were highlighted in blue, as their impairments could potentially impact similar regions of the brain. However, there was only one subject who met that criteria.

The case studies that referenced specific impairments were then tallied and sorted based on which area of the brain they were impaired in. As the study focused on the four lobes, results were divided into the occipital, frontal, parietal and temporal categories. There were additional areas of the brain referenced, which were then sorted into overarching categories of the brain such as the corpus callosum, the ventricles, and the insula and striatum. A tally was made for what side of the brain subjects were impaired in. Some of the subjects were impaired in several areas, all of which were counted (e.g. if the left ventricle and left parieto-occipital area were mentioned, “left” would be counted twice, and both the parietal and occipital areas would be counted once). All dyslexic subjects were excluded from this count due to their cause being “unknown”, but were counted in a separate analysis due to the large number of dyslexic subjects in the study.

This method was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Research Board.

Results

Twenty-nine studies specified the cause of impairment, with eight of those being strokes

(five unspecified) and two of those being some form of syphilis. The left hemisphere of the brain was the most common term mentioned at 24 times, four times the amount of its right hemispheric counterpart, which had six mentions. The results of the rest of the data can be summarized in the table below.

Area of Impairment	Amount of Times Mentioned
Temporal Lobe	12
Occipital Lobe	8
Parietal Lobe	7
Corpus Callosum	3
Ventricles	2
Frontal Lobe	1
Insula and Striatum	1

The temporal lobe was the most frequently affected area, with 12 mentions of impairment. It controls the processing of language and auditory information (Cleveland Clinic, 2023). Two of those mentions were specifically about impairments in Wernicke's area, which

plays a big role in language processing and speech production (Binder, 2015). The occipital lobe controls vision, and was the second most affected area, with eight mentions of impairment. The parietal lobe, which controls the motor skills and the processing of sensory information, had seven mentions (Jawabri & Sharma, 2023). The corpus callosum had three mentions, all of which were in the splenium, which is used to facilitate communication between the temporal and occipital lobes (Blaauw & Meiners, 2020); the ventricles had two mentions, both of which described cortical atrophy alongside the enlargement of the ventricles; the frontal lobe had one mention; and the insula and striatum had one mention.

The broader demographics of the study were diverse. Of the 82 subjects who were recorded, 42 of them were adults, while 16 were minors and 24 were unspecified. 23 subjects were male, while 24 subjects were female and 35 subjects were unspecified. 17 subjects were in a career that heavily revolved around music (instrumentalist, professor, composer, and instrument teacher) while 6 were actively studying or had completed music degrees at the undergraduate or graduate level.

The broader trends across the database show that 57% (42) of the 82 subjects were dyslexic. Dyslexia impairs the ability to read written language and primarily affects left hemispheric areas in the temporal lobe, the occipito-temporal area, and the tempo-parietal area (Norton et al., 2016). 16 subjects reported their math ability, of which 75% (12) of them struggled with reading mathematical symbols and/or doing basic mathematical operations. 28 subjects did not have trouble with listening to music, while 10 subjects did. Eight subjects noted specifically struggling with rhythm, while five had difficulty with telling left and right apart. Five subjects definitively reported on their state recovery, with two not progressing at all and three in various stages of recovery.

Discussion

The findings support the idea that reading musical syntax requires a vast neural network; however, the requisite functions seem skewed to the left. Dysmusia seems to predominantly affect the left side of the brain, which is more associated with language and mathematical processes (Corballis, 2014). Notably, two key areas that were mentioned to light up earlier — Broca's area and Wernicke's area — both reside on the left side of the brain (Corballis, 2014). This contradicts the theory that musical syntax is dominantly processed on the right side of the brain while language is processed on the left. The right side of the brain is more associated with creativity and spatial processing, and was mentioned six times. This indicates that reading musical syntax requires both parts of the brain, even if the left side seems more critical. This also aligns with general findings that the left and right sides of the brain tend to work in tandem to perform most functions (Cleveland Clinic, 2023). This is further evidenced by repeated mentions of the splenium, which connects the lobe controlling vision and the lobe controlling the processing of language. The splenium was damaged in conjunction with the left occipital lobe, but two of its three occurrences revolved around a patient who had a damaged occipital lobe and splenium but an undamaged temporal lobe.

Within the lobes, the temporal lobe was the most prominently mentioned. It has a variety of functions, and many of the case studies were vague about what specific parts of the temporal lobe were being impaired. It is notable for managing emotions, processing sensory information, encoding memories, and interpreting language (Cleveland Clinic, 2023). Wernicke's area in particular is notable for its role in language processing and speech production. Impairments to the temporal lobe can often lead to difficulties in the formation of memory, visual agnosia, and

difficulty understanding languages, frequent symptoms of dyslexia (Queensland Health, 2022; U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2025; Mayo Clinic, 2022). Impairment to the right temporal lobe can impair the ability to discriminate between different sounds and recognition of melodic and tonal sequences, impairments that are frequently studied alongside dysmusia (Sato et al., 2003). Impairment to the left temporal lobe can impair the ability to understand languages (Queensland Health, 2022.). This suggests that the networks needed to understand language and musical syntax, while distinct, are fairly similar. 47% of subjects being dyslexic further supports this hypothesis. From this study, it seems highly likely that dyslexia is comorbid to dysmusia, with both requiring similar areas of the brain. The occipital and parietal lobes were also frequently mentioned. The occipital lobe governs vision, and it stands to reason that the ability to visually process the world around us is crucial for the ability to see musical syntax. The parietal lobe processes sensory information while also focusing on spatial awareness. Its frequency of mention supports the theory that spatial awareness is a crucial component of musical syntax, and that impairment of spatial awareness can uniquely impair the comprehension of musical syntax while leaving other reading functions intact. It is important to note that reading letters also activates the parietal lobe, but that the areas of activation differ (Sergent et al., 1992).

Musical listening ability and musical reading ability do not appear to be correlated, with 73% of subjects saying they did not struggle with musical listening ability. In fact, in case studies that interviewed the subjects, they often discussed ways to deal with their deficiency in reading music, and “remembering the tune” was frequently suggested (Ganschow et al., 1994). Some subjects reported no impairment in singing or any other production of music that involved a melody (Horikoshi et al., 1997). The reason behind the lack of correlation is unclear with the current research. One possible explanation is that prior researchers were correct to assume that

melodic abilities primarily lay in the right hemisphere of the brain, as brain scans revealed higher frequency of activation in the right hemisphere (Maess et al., 2001). However, it is possible they were incorrect in assuming that the syntactic musical reading capability utilized the same neural systems as musical listening did.

Finally, very few subjects recovered. Many of the subjects did not definitively answer yes or no for whether they were recovered in their respective studies, but many mentioned having struggled with it their entire lives and presumably never recovered. A significant amount of those struggling musicians were dyslexic, which is a disability that cannot be recovered from. Others struggled with the dysmusia after suffering strokes or undergoing surgeries that impaired or removed areas that were irrecoverable. Even among the subjects who were mentioned to be recovering, mentions were made of “improving performance” but not of full recovery.

The other regions of the brain were not significant enough to be discussed due to being referenced too few times.

Limitations

There were four main limitations in this study. The first major limitation stems from the lack of accessible studies online. Many studies were extremely old and had never been digitized, making it impossible to gain access to them. Some are in foreign languages like French and were unable to be interpreted by a non-French speaker. Others are paywalled and could not be accessed due to a lack of funding. As a result, many of the case studies referenced in the spreadsheet were not directly looked at, being based instead on the information other studies provided, either in references or in systematic reviews. This causes potential issues with misinformation stemming from potential miscommunications or misattributions arising from the

word-of-mouth method used to gather many of the sources. It also led to many inaccessible case studies having several “unknowns” in the categories, as many of the referencing authors had little reason to list all the information those case studies provided. This led to potential information being lost, particularly in the demographics and recovery sections.

The second major limitation is the lack of specificity in the studies being used. Many of these studies have vague descriptions for areas of the brain (e.g. the area of impairment referenced simply as the “temporal lobe”). This forced the results to be sorted based off of the four main lobes of the brain and other major areas; however, the brain is incredibly complex and each area of the brain performs a variety of different functions. Insufficient information was provided in the case studies used in this meta analyses to properly differentiate specific areas of the brain that were causing the impairments. This makes the study unable to isolate any particular cause of the dysmusia; instead it can only implicate broad areas of the brain that were involved, which is also a possible reason why the regions that were implicated overlapped so much with reading. While it could also be because the functions genuinely do have a wide overlap, there is no way to tell in this study. It is also important to note that the temporal lobe is the area most prone to seizures, and the high mentions may have been mistakenly correlated to functional importance when it could instead simply be due to the temporal lobe simply being the most prone to damage (NYU Langone Health, n.d.).

The third major limitation is the sampling biases in the studies that were available. Many of these paywalled studies were referenced from studies that were specifically looking for dyslexic subjects to see if there was a correlation between dyslexia and dysmusia, resulting in a disproportionately high number of case studies who had dyslexia. This may have artificially inflated the results and caused a higher correlation between dyslexia and dysmusia than there

would have been otherwise. There may also be a sampling bias in the case studies themselves, as those who had the resources to identify dyslexia were more likely to admit they struggled with reading letters, and as such were more likely to admit they struggled with reading musical syntax.

Lastly, the possibility of human error must be accounted for. The filtering of the studies and the subsequent counts and sortings of the impacted areas were done by one individual, and their judgements may differ from another individual. The filterings had a layer of subjectivity in what counted as a reference to reading musical syntax or comprehending music as a language, which could result in some studies being excluded when they did fit the criteria. Some case studies were conducted on individuals who, for whatever reason, did not struggle with reading musical syntax, and it was also possible those studies were accidentally included, skewing the dataset. It was also possible to miscount the amount of times any specific brain area was mentioned. While the mentioned regions of the brain were organized into the four lobes along with additional areas, those “additional areas” were classified by looking at the actual data and determining an overarching area they belonged to (corpus callosum, insula and striatum, etc) — again, a subjective point that could theoretically skew the results.

Conclusion

The main goal of this study was to provide a large and comprehensive dataset for future researchers to reference more easily in the future. From now on, this study will serve as an accessible set of data points for anyone interested in researching the field in the future.

The secondary purpose of this study was to identify the underlying trends found in individuals who had impaired abilities to read sheet music. This study identified several key

trends, both in the affected areas of the brain and in the difficulties individuals who struggled with dysmusia identified. The left side of the brain was identified as the primary area governing the processing of musical syntax, with the left temporal lobe the biggest contributor. The left temporal lobe controls the processing of language, the impairment of which can lead to difficulty reading words – a comorbidity often found in dysmusia. Regions in the parietal and occipital lobes were also identified as areas of interest, and it is recommended that future research focus on the left temporal lobe and what specific areas process syntax, while also looking more deeply into how the parietal and occipital lobes affect musical syntax processing. It is also recommended to look into the processing similarities between dysmusia and dyscalculia, as there are high occurrence rates of math and spatial struggles within those who reported their math ability.

Lastly, the study has significant implications for disproving the connection between the capability for musical listening and the capability for musical reading. The lack of correlation between the two variables in this meta analysis and melody-based coping strategies referenced by individual case studies provide strong evidence for the two systems being separate. Future researchers are encouraged to look into these topics as distinct phenomena instead of a conjoined one as so many are doing currently. This will lead to less false correlations in future studies, as the two phenomena can each have studies conducted into their individual causes, symptoms, and solutions, allowing for more specific explanations in the two distinct fields and better targeted supports granted to individuals who suffer from either affliction.

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Appendix

Case Study Dataset

Specific Brain Area Dyslexic Neurodivergent (Not Dyslexia) Stroke (Unspecified)

Age Noted	Sex	Background	Recovery?	Cause	Music Reading	Text Reading	Music Listening	Numbers/Mathematics	Source
?	?	Former violinist	?	Angioma and surgery affecting left temporal lobe, left parietal lobe, left occipital lobe	Y	Y	N	Y	Dorgeuille, 1966
52	M	Composer	N	Cerebral atrophy with bilateral ventricular enlargement	Y	?	N	?	Henson, 1988, Alajouanine, 1948
58	M	Music teacher (guitar)	?	Enlargement of lateral and third ventricles, cortical atrophy (more on the left than right). Possible Alzheimer's	Y	Y	N	?	Polk and Kertesz, 1993
?	?	Keyboards, singer, violin	?	Glioblastoma, affecting the left temporal lobe	Y	Y	Y	?	Dorgeuille, 1966
42	M	Professional jazz bassist	?	Hemorrhage affecting left posterior temporal lobe and inferior parietal lobes	Y	Y	Y	N	Brust, 1980
?	?	Teacher, violin student	?	Hemorrhage affecting the right insula, striatum	Y	?	?	?	Finkelnburg, 1870
77	M	Composer-conductor, retired professor of music	Y	Hemorrhagic infarction of the left occipitotemporal area	Y	Y	N	?	Judd et al., 1983

58	F	Piano teacher	?	Infarction from the left superior temporal gyrus to the angular gyrus in Wernicke's area	Y	Y	N	?	Midorikawa et al., 2003
72	M	Longtime piano hobbyist	Y	Infarction in the right supramarginal gyrus and angular gyri with surrounding oedema	Y	N	Y	Y	McDonald, 2006
26	F	Piano teacher	?	Intracerebral hematoma caused by an arteriovenous malformation of the left occipital parasplenic region. Surgery was performed to remove the lesion. Afterwards, damage remained in the occipito-temporal deep white matter surrounding the trigone, the posterior horn of the left lateral ventricle and the splenium of the corpus callosum. Decreased cerebral blood flow in the left occipital lobe and posterior part of the temporoparietal lobe	Y	Y	N	?	Horikoshi et al., 1997
?	?	?	?	Left temporo-parietal lobe	Y	Y	?	?	Schön et al., (2001)
64	M	Light music, piano, bass	?	Lesion in left temporal lobe from embolic stroke	Y	Y	N	?	Assal, 1973
?	?	Drummer	?	Meningioma and surgery affecting left occipital lobe and splenium	Y	Y	N	Y	Levin and Rose, 1979
53	F	School teacher (piano)	?	Parietooccipital atrophy (more on the right)	Y	N	N	?	Polk and Kertesz, 1993

67	F	Pianist	?	Posterior cortical atrophy of the left hemisphere	Y	Y	N	Y	Sacks, 2010
?	?	?	?	Postero-lateral border of the left ventricle and hypodense left parieto-occipital area	Y	Y	?	?	Hofman et al., 1993
?	?	Teacher, violin, voice	?	Stroke	Y	?	Y	?	Jossman, 1927
?	M	Businessman, singer	?	Stroke affecting left occipital lobe and splenium	Y	Y	N	N	Dejerine, 1892
?	M	Professional violinist	?	Stroke that caused mild Wernicke's aphasia and right hemiparesis	Y	Y	Y	?	Wertheim and Botez, 1961
?	?	Violinist	Y	Stroke(?)	Y	Y	N	?	Anton, 1888
?	?	?	?	Stroke(?)	Y	Y	N	Y	Bernhardt, 1872
?	?	Physician	?	Stroke(?)	Y	Y	?	N	Holmes, 1950
?	?	Businessman	?	Stroke(?)	Y	Y	N	Y	Pötzl, 1927
?	?	Professor of music	?	Syphilis	Y	?	N	?	Charcot, 1886
?	?	Merchant, violinist	?	Syphilis?	Y	N	Y	?	Frankl-Hochwart, 1891
22	F	Voice student, piano, guitar	?	Tumor and surgery affecting left temporal lobe and left parietal lobe	Y	Y	N	?	Brust, 1980
?	?	Popular singer, guitar, piano	?	Tumor and surgery affecting the left frontal lobe	Y	Y	Y	Y	Jellinek, 1956
34	F	Professional musician	?	Two lesions, one in the left posterior temporal region (left temporoparietal region) and one in the right parietooccipital region. Caused by a hemorrhagic encephalitis presumably caused by herpes	Y	N	Y	Y	Cappelletti et al., 2000
10	M	Piano player	N	Unknown	Y	?	N	?	Henson, 1997
12	F	Plano player	?	Unknown	Y	Y	N	?	Gordon, 2000

?	?	Composer, teacher	?	Unknown	Y	Y	N	N	Fischer, 1867
?	?	?	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Proust, 1866
? (Young)	F	?	?	Unknown	Y	Y	?	Y	Fisher, 1905
24	F	University student studying vocal music	?	Unknown	Y	Y	N	?	Hébert et al., 2008
18	F	Student at the Royal College of Music	?	Unknown	Y	Y	N	?	Critchley, 1970
?	F	Flutist	?	Unknown	Y	Y	?	?	Oldfield, 1987
16	?	Pianist	?	Unknown	Y	Y	?	?	Miles, 1993
20	F	Voice major at university Music Conservatory	?	Unknown	Y	Y	N	Y	Ganschow et al., 1994
? (youngish)	F	Master's student in voice at a music conservatory	?	Unknown	Y	Y	?	?	Ganschow et al., 1994
? (college student)	M	Studied music in college and then switched to history	?	Unknown	Y	Y	N	?	Ganschow et al., 1994
?	F	Studied music in college and then switched majors	?	Unknown	Y	Y	?	?	Ganschow et al., 1994
? (Mid 30s)	M	Violinist	?	Unknown	Y	Y	?	?	Ganschow et al., 1994
? (Older than 30)	F	Professional pianist	?	Unknown	Y	Y	?	?	Ganschow et al., 1994
8	F	Has begun learning the recorder	?	Unknown	Y	Y	?	Y	Geiger, 2015
? (adult)	M	Plays trumpet	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Miles, 1996
? (child)	M	Plays trumpet	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Miles, 1996
? (Adult)	F	Studied vocals in university	?	Unknown	Y	Y	N	?	Ashcroft, 2019
16	M	Played guitar, switched to piano, switched to tuba, also plays trombone and bass guitar	?	Unknown	Y	Y	N	?	Ashcroft, 2019
? (College graduate)	M	Completed bachelor of music	?	Unknown	Y	N	N	?	Ashcroft, 2019

17	F	Completed Year 12 VCAL equivalence in visual arts. Played guitar in grade 3 for one year before quitting. Learned how to sight read in high school	?	Unknown	Y	Y	Y	?	Ashcroft, 2019
? (Adult)	M	Associate principal brass player with a major U.S. orchestra	?	Unknown	Y	Y	?	?	Nelson, 2016
? (Adult)	M	founder of a recording company	?	Unknown	Y	Y	N	?	Nelson, 2016
? (Adult)	M	professor of music at a major university	?	Unknown	Y	Y	N	?	Nelson, 2016
Young (In university, undergrad or grad)	M	Percussion	?	Unknown	Y	Y	?	?	Solook, 2015
? (Late 30s)	F	Begins taking piano lessons	?	Unknown	Y	Y	?	?	Vladikovic, 2013
7	M	Begins taking piano lessons	?	Unknown	Y	Y	?	?	Vladikovic, 2013
? (Adult)	?	Piano, trombone, flute, saxophone, guitar	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Poole, 2001
? (Adult)	?	Recorder, voice	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Smith, 2001
? (Child)	F	Piano	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Ditchfield, 2001
? (Adult)	?	Flute	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Oldfield, 2001
? (Adult)	?	Cello, guitar, voice	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Lea, 2001, 2008
? (Adult)	?	Voice, harp	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Wood, 2001, 2008
? (Adult)	M	Percussion, voice	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Backhouse, 2001
? (Adult)	?	Recorder, trumpet, cornet, piano	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Clarke, 2001
? (Adult)	?	Unknown	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Coker, 2001
? (Adult)	?	Unknown	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Apostoli, 2008
? (Adult)	F	Voice, piano	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Bishop-Liebler, 2008

? (Adult)	F	Voice, saxophone, flute	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Bishop-Liebler, 2008
? (Adult)	F	Voice, piano	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Bishop-Liebler, 2008
? (Child)	M	Piano	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Oglethorpe, 2002
? (Child)	?	Piano	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Oglethorpe, 2002
? (Adult)	?	Piano	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Oglethorpe, 2002
? (Child)	?	Piano	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Oglethorpe, 2002
11	?	Piano	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Oglethorpe, 2002
? (Child)	?	Violin	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Oglethorpe, 2002
? (Adult)	?	Trumpeter	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Oglethorpe, 2002
8	?	Piano	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Oglethorpe, 2002
? (Adult)	?	Organ	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Wade, 2006
? (Adult)	?	?	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Crawford, 2015
? (Child)	M	Piano	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Proctor, 2000
? (Child)	F	Flute, piano	?	Unknown	Y	?	?	?	Knapp, 2007
?	?	Former violinist	?	Unknown, affected left temporal lobe?	Y	N	Y	Y	Dorgeuille, 1966